

**REVIEW OF THE GENUS *MALLOTA* MEIGEN, 1822 (DIPTERA, SYRPHIDAE)
IN POLAND**

**PRZEGLĄD RODZAJU *MALLOTA* MEIGEN, 1822 (DIPTERA, SYRPHIDAE)
W POLSCE**

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ABSTRACT. This publication summarizes faunistic information about the genus *Mallota* Meigen, 1822 (Diptera, Syrphidae) in Poland, based on the study of specimens deposited in museums and private collections, as well as authors' field research. All four species occurring in Poland are rare and endangered, listed on the red list of threatened animals in Poland and present in the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. Distribution maps, photographs and a key to all species occurring in Poland are given.

KEY WORDS: flower flies, hoverflies, threatened, endangered species, new records, Poland, IUCN

INTRODUCTION

Mallota Meigen, 1822 (Diptera: Syrphidae) is a widely distributed but rare genus of hover flies, found in the Holarctic and in the Afrotropical, Neotropical and Oriental regions, with around 70 species (Krivosheina 2002, Thompson *et al.* 2010). In recent years a few new species have been described (Thompson & Zumbado 2002, Hirooka *et al.* 2015, Thompson 2019). In Poland, the presence of four species has been confirmed so far: *M. cimbiciformis* (Fallén, 1817), *M. fuciformis* (Fabricius, 1794), *M. megilliformis* (Fallén, 1817) and *M. tricolor* Loew, 1871, out of seven species occurring in Europe.

Adults are large flies resembling bees or bumblebees. They are similar to some other genera of hoverflies occurring in Europe: *Brachypalpus* Macquart, 1834, *Criorhina* Meigen, 1822, *Eristalis* Latreille, 1804, *Merodon* Meigen, 1803 and *Myathropa* Rondani, 1845. Representatives of the genus *Mallota* are characterized as follows: face with facial knob; antennae short; arista almost bare; wing vein R₄₊₅ deeply curved, with the vein M₁ meeting it at an acute angle; wing cell M open at wing margin; hind femora stout, and in the case of some species swollen and arcuate; hind tibiae flattened.

Described larvae of *Mallota* are highly specialized saprophages equipped with a tube-like breathing siphon at the posterior end (fig. 1c) that allows them to breathe while submerged in water rich with organic debris. They develop in standing water-filled rot-holes of mature trees. Distinctive features of larvae of this genus are a smooth body surface and three pairs of projections on the sides near the base of the siphon (Rotheray 1993). Immature stages of *M. fuciformis*, *M. megilliformis* and *M. tricolor* have not been described so far.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The examined material and data come from the authors' own field research on hoverflies and from their survey in museum collections: (MIZ PAS - Museum and Institute of Zoology, Polish Academy of Sciences; NHUL - Natural History Museum, University of Łódź; MNHW - Museum of Natural History, Wrocław University), and in the private collections of B. Soszyński, J.K. Kowalczyk, Z. Mocarski and C. Bystrowski. Specimens of the species occurring in Poland but collected in other countries or with unknown country of origin, were used for comparison. These are also listed in the material sections of this paper. Photographs were taken by the authors unless otherwise stated. Various digital cameras were used.

The MapaUTM ver. 5.1 program was used to generate the geographical distribution maps. The available literature from Poland was analyzed in order to provide complete citations.

RESULTS

Information and data about *Mallota* from within the current borders of Poland can be found in the publications of Bachmann (1858), Nowicki (1873), Sznabl (1881), Czwalina (1893), Schroeder (1909, 1911), Karl (1935), Trojanowa-Bańkowska (1959), Bańkowska (1961, 1982), Banaszak (1988), Kowalczyk & Watała (1991), Kowalczyk *et al.* (1998), Soszyński (1999), Pisarska & Soszyński (2001), Kowalczyk & Majecki (2002), Kowalczyk & Garbalewski (2004), Soszyński *et al.* (2010), Soszyński & Soszyńska-Maj (2011), Witek *et al.* (2015) and Żóralski & Kowalczyk (2015, 2017, 2017b). These reports comprise, however, a small number of specimens in total, and some of these papers are even synthetic publications in which the authors mentioned the occurrence of the species in a given area on a basis of previous reports. The oldest specimens have not survived to our time, but luckily most of the material was available for review and there were no errors in the identifications.

During the survey, 98 adult individuals of *Mallota* from the current territory of Poland were analyzed, representing the following four species: *M. cimbiciformis*, *M. fuciformis*, *M. megilliformis* and *M. tricolor*. In addition, another 33 individuals of this genus from outside of Poland or of unknown locality were identified and used for comparison. Much of the material published in this paper is based on new specimens collected over the past two decades.

Flowers visited and breeding sites in Poland are based on the authors' observations and are summarized in TAB. 1.

SPECIES LIST

***Mallota cimbiciformis* (Fallén, 1817)**

= *Syrphus cimbiciformis* Fallén, 1817

= *M. erystaloides* Loew, 1856

= *M. cristalloides* Schiner, 1864 [misspelling of *erystaloides* Loew]

MATERIAL EXAMINED (13 ♂♂, 4 ♀♀, 10 exx. larvae, 5 exx. ova). **POLAND. Southern Baltic Coasts (= Pobrzeża Południowobałtyckie).** The Beech Forest near Szczecin = „Stettin, Buchheide” [VV71], 22 VI 1908, 1 ♂, leg. G. Schroeder, coll. MIZ PAS (Schroeder 1909, Karl 1935). **Southern Baltic Lakes (= Pojezierza Południowobałtyckie).** Poznań: Dendrological Garden of the University of Life Sciences [XU21], on a *Populus* trunk, 31 V 2011, 1 ♂, leg. et coll. P. Trzciński. Swarzędz [XU41], 6 VI 2015, 1 ♂, on poplar *Populus nigra* trunk at the entrance to the tree hollow, leg. et coll. A. Skitek. Swarzędz [XU30], 1 VI 2016, 1 ♀, meadow – on flowers of green spurge *Euphorbia esula*, leg. et coll. A. Skitek. Gortatowo [XU41], 7 VII 2015, 1 ♀, flying in chestnut *Aesculus hippocastanum* hollow, female laid eggs – 5 of them preserved in EtOH75%, leg. et coll. A. Skitek, 5 III 2017, imago (room conditions): 12 IV 2017, 1 ♂, 2 exx. 3rd instar larvae preserved in EtOH75%, chestnut *Aesculus hippocastanum* hollow, leg. et coll. ex larva, coll. A. Skitek; 8 III 2017, 1 ex. larva preserved in EtOH75%, the same as mentioned above, leg. et coll. A. Skitek. Poznań [XU30], 22 III 2017, 7 exx. 3rd instar larvae preserved in EtOH75%, fig. 1c, maple *Acer platanoides* hollow, fig. 1d, leg.

A. Skitek, 2 exx. coll. Ł. Mielczarek, 4 exx. coll. A. Skitek, 1 ex. coll. R. Żóralski; 1 IV 2017, adults (room conditions): 11 V 2017, 1 ♂, 20 V 2017, 1 ♀, the same as mentioned above, leg. et cult. ex larvae, coll. A. Skitek; 12 IV 2018, adults (room conditions): 15-16 V 2018, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, the same as mentioned above, leg. et cult. ex larvae, coll. A. Skitek; 8 V 2018, 1 ♂, flying around maple *Acer platanoides* hollow; 7 VI 2018, 1 ♂, on maple *Acer platanoides* trunk at the entrance to the tree hollow, leg. et coll. A. Skitek; 20 VI 2021, 3 ♂♂, on leaves of *Aegopodium podagraria* and flying around maple *Acer platanoides* hollow, fig. 1e. **Central Polish Lowlands (= Niziny Środkowopolskie)**. Sochaczew distr. Trojanów [DC48], 2 VI 1957, 1 ♂, leg. A. Mońko, coll. MIZ PAS (Trojanowa-Bańkowska 1959, Bańkowska 1961, Bańkowska 1982). **Małopolska Uplands (= Wyżyna Małopolska)**. Kielce [DB73], 25 V 1954, 1 ♂, fig. 1a, 1b, leg. J. Karczewski, coll. MIZ PAS (Trojanowa-Bańkowska 1959, Bańkowska 1961, Żóralski et Kowalczyk 2017b).

DIAGNOSTIC FEATURES. In general appearance and size it resembles other bee-like hoverflies, i.a. *Eristalis tenax* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Criorhina asilica* (Fallén, 1816), *Criorhina pachymera* (Egger, 1858), *Brachypalpus valgus* Panzer, 1798 and *B. laphriformis* (Fallén, 1816) but differs from them by the wing venation and characteristic shape, length and dusting of the face, with a shining black facial knob. Eyes bare, in males touching at a point; postpedicel orange-brown; abdomen covered with short adjacent hairs; mesoscutal hairs unicolorous and light brown, without admixture of black hairs; scutellum yellow-brown. Larva of this species was described by Maibach & Goeldlin (1989) and Krivosheina (2002).

BIOLOGY. Flight period in Poland is from the end of May to the beginning of July. Larvae develop in tree-holes of various deciduous trees, filled with standing water. Adult males were observed resting near the trunk cavities of *Acer platanoides* L., *Aesculus hippocastanum* L. and *Populus nigra* L. waiting for females attracted to predictable oviposition sites. Males aggressively defended their position against intruders of the same genus and other groups of insects. Adults were reared from the larvae collected in a hollow of *A. platanoides*; the breeding of larvae collected in a *A. hippocastanum* hollow was unsuccessful.

DISTRIBUTION. Europe, North Africa, Near East (Pennards *et al.* 2021a). In Poland known from several sites, some of which are located around Poznań (fig. 1f). In a larger number (10 males and 3 females) reported only from Bukowa Natural Forest near Szczecin (Schroeder 1909); one specimen proving that observation is present in MIZ PAS collection. Except records published in the material sections, *M. cimbiciformis* was found in further vicinity of Stettin:

6 VI 1910, 1 male, on *Aegopodium* L. (Schroeder 1911), in Murowana Goślina near Poznań [XU32] (Banaszak 1988) and in Łutownia near Budy [FD84] (8 VII 1996, section: 307/308, leg. S. Turnhout), during one of the summer camps organized by Dutch Youth Organization for Nature Study (NJV) in Poland in Białowieża. The latter was recorded in moist environment and was recorded among typical set of marsh species: *Pyrophaena* Schiner, 1860, *Tropidia scita* (Harris, 1776), *Chalcosyrphus nemorum* (Fabricius, 1805), *Helophilus* Meigen, 1822, *Anasimyia* Schiner, 1864, *Parhelophilus* Girschner, 1897 (Dijkstra & Kalkman 1997).

CONSERVATION. Species listed in the “Red List of Threatened Animals in Poland” (Palaczyk *et al.* 2002) in category EN (endangered) and in the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species (Pennards *et al.* 2021a) in category LC (Least Concern).

FIG 1. *Mallota cimbiciformis* (Fallén, 1817). a) male, dorsal view; b) male lateral view; c) larva; d) hollow in *Acer platanoides* in which the larva was found; e) living male specimen observed later near the same hollow; f) distribution in Poland: ● verified data, based on material examined, ▲ unverified data

***Mallota fuciformis* (Fabricius, 1794)**

= *Syrphus fuciformis* Fabricius, 1794

= *Musca fusiformis* Turton, 1801 [new name for *fuciformis* Fabricius]

MATERIAL EXAMINED: (16 ♂♂, 21 ♀♀, 1 ex. fragment of exuvium, 1 ex. mummified pupa, 3 exx. ova). **POLAND. Southern Baltic Coasts.** Gdynia: Krykulec Glade in Trójmiejski Landscape Park [CF34], 27 V 2003, 1 ♂, leg. J.K. Kowalczyk (Kowalczyk & Garbalewski 2004, Żóralski & Kowalczyk 2015). Gdynia: Śląska street [CF34], 16 V 2010, 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀ (published incorrectly as male), 30 V 2010, 1 ♂, leg. J.K. Kowalczyk (Żóralski & Kowalczyk 2015). Gdynia-Redłowo: Polanka Redłowska [CF44], 26 IV 2016, 1 ♂, leg. J.K. Kowalczyk (Żóralski & Kowalczyk 2017). Darżłubska Forest: springs of the Gizdepka river near Rekowo Górne [CF25], 24 IV 2020, 1 ♂, fig. 2d, on *Prunus* spp., leg. R. Żóralski. Trójmiejski Landscape Park near Reda [CF25], 8 V 2020, 1 ♀, fig. 2g, on *Crataegus* spp., 29 IV 2021, 1 ♂, fig. 2a, 2b, on *Prunus* spp., 22 V 2021, 2 ♀♀, on *Crataegus* spp., leg. R. Żóralski. Kartoszyño [CF16], 1 ♂, on *Crataegus* spp., 30 V 2021, leg. R. Żóralski. **Southern Baltic Lakes.** Wielkopolski National Park: Osowa Góra [XT29], 18 V 2006, 1 ♀, leg. P. Trzciński. Wielkopolski National Park: strict protection area "Mixed Forest on Morena" [XT29], 16 IV 2007, 1 ♀, 15 V 2007, 1 ♂, leg. P. Trzciński. Swarzędz [XU30], 19 V 2015, 1 ♂, on flowers of hawthorn *Crataegus* spp., leg. A. Skitek. Gortatowo [XU41], fig. 2e, 2f, 2 V 2016, 2 ♀♀, flying near the entrance of chestnut *Aesculus hippocastanum* hollow, one of females laid eggs - 3 of them preserved in EtOH75%, 7 V 2016, 5 ♀♀, 19 V 2016, 1 ♀, the same as mentioned above, leg. A. Skitek. Poznań [XU30], 22 III 2017, adults (room condition), fig. 2c: 1 IV 2017, 1 ♂, 2 IV 2017, 1 ♂, 4 IV 2017, 1 ♀, 1 ex. fragment of exuvium, 1 ex. damaged and mummified pupa, buried shallow in the ground near maple *Acer platanoides* hollow, leg. et cult. ex pupae A. Skitek. Poznań: Nowe Miasto, Eastern Green Belt [XU30], 9 V 2022, 1 ♂, 1 ♀, on flowers of *Prunus* spp., a male hovering above feeding female, female laid eggs. **Central Polish Lowlands.** Wrocław [XS46], 5 V 1953 (published as 5 VI 1953), 1 ♀, leg. A. Mońko, coll. MIZ PAS (Trojanowa-Bańkowska 1959), 24 IV 1979, 1 ♀, leg. T. Zatwarnicki, det. B. Soszyński. Spalski Landscape Park: Konewka [DC41], 23 IV 2015, 2 ♂♂, on *Prunus* spp., 24 IV 2015, 1 ♀, leg. R. Żóralski, 24 IV 2015, 1 ♂, 26 IV 2015, 1 ♀, leg. Z. Mocarski (Witek *et al.* 2015). Spalski Landscape Park: Ceteń [DC50], 27 IV 2015, 1 ♀, leg. Ł. Mielczarek (Witek *et al.* 2015).

DIAGNOSTIC FEATURES. Distinguished from other bumblebee-mimic species of the genus, *M. tricolor* and *M. megilliformis*, by hairy eyes, rounder shape of the abdomen and body covered by black and orange hair. Males of *M. fuciformis* have eyes widely separated.

BIOLOGY. *Mallota fuciformis* has the earliest phenological appearance of all European *Mallota*. In Poland adults were observed at the end of April and in May. It is characterized by an almost ideal bumblebee mimic. Both males and females of *M. fuciformis* can be seen flying on top of flowering wild living fruit trees: plums and cherries *Prunus* L. and later on hawthorn *Crataegus* L. Compared to more common *Criorhina ranunculi* (Panzer, 1804) and *Eristalis intricaria* (Linnaeus, 1758) being active at that time, flight of *Mallota fuciformis* is much faster and more dynamic. The intensive orange hair at the end of the abdomen glistening in the sun allows a careful observer to recognize this species in flight. Rearing of larvae were unsuccessful but emerging from pupae collected near maple *Acer platanoides* hollow succeeded.

FIG 2. *Mallota fuciformis* (Fabricius, 1794). a) male, dorsal view; b) male lateral view; c) freshly emerged specimen with unfolded wings; d) male specimen; e) *Aesculus hippocastanum* near which an ovipositing female was observed; f) zoom into the hollow of other tree where females were observed; g) female specimen; h) distribution in Poland: ● verified data, based on material examined

DISTRIBUTION. West Palearctic species, having in Poland, Latvia, Lithuania, Belarus and European parts of Russia its northeastern border of the range (Pennards *et al.* 2021b). In Poland, it is known from a small number of localities (fig. 2h) although in the areas where it occurs, it was regularly found over the last few years. According to Schroeder (1909) followed by Karl (1935), 2 ex. of *M. fuciformis* were also collected by Triepke in Garz (Germany, close to the current border with Poland) as were seen by him in the collection of Marienstifts-Gymnasiums in Szczecin [= Stettin].

CONSERVATION. Species listed in the “Red List of Threatened Animals in Poland” (Palaczyk *et al.* 2002) in category EN (endangered). Because the species seems to be expanding its range in the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species (Pennards *et al.* 2021b) in category LC (Least Concern).

***Mallota megilliformis* (Fallén, 1817)**

= *Syrphus megilliformis* Fallén, 1817

MATERIAL EXAMINED: (18 ♂♂, 7 ♀♀). **POLAND. Southern Baltic Coasts.** The Beech Forest near Szczecin = „Stettin, Buchheide” [VV71], 22 VI 1908, 1 ♂, “specimen without head”, leg. G. Schroeder, coll. MIZ PAS. **Southern Baltic Lakes.** Soczewka, near Skrwa river [DD02], 28 VI 1971, 1 ♀, leg. B. Soszyński. Strugaj near Piwnicki Forest Nature Reserve [CD38], 5 VII 1977, 1 ♀, leg. T. Pawlikowski, det. B. Soszyński. **Eastern Baltic Lakes (= Pojezierza Wschodniobałtyckie).** Zelwa [FE58], 31 V 2018, 1 ♂, leg. Ł. Mielczarek, 1 ♂, on foliage near alder carr, leg. A. Skitek, 1 VI 2018, 1 ♂, on *Sambucus nigra*, leg. C. Bystrowski. Augustów Primeval Forest: Stanowisko [FE68], 1 VI 2018, 1 ♀, leg. Ł. Mielczarek. **Podlasie-Belarus Uplands (= Wysoczyzny Podlasko-Białoruskie).** Augustów Primeval Forest: Rubcowo [FE66], 16 VI 1977, 1 ♀, leg. B. Soszyński. **Central Polish Lowlands.** Zdziar-Łopatki ad. Staroźreby, alder carr near Płonka river [DD33], 26 V 1971, 1 ♂ 2 ♀♀, leg. J.K. Kowalczyk, det. B. Soszyński. Rogów ad. Skierniewice [DC24], 1 VI 1973, 1 ♂, leg. M. Dąbrowski, det. B. Soszyński. Lublinek Forest in Łódź [CC83], 1 VI 1981, 2 ♂♂, leg. B. Soszyński (Soszyński & Soszyńska-Maj 2011). Kalonka near Łódź [DC04], 16 V 1986, 1 ♂, leg. J.K. Kowalczyk, coll. NHUL (Kowalczyk & Watała 1991, Kowalczyk *et al.* 1998, Kowalczyk & Majecki 2002, Soszyński *et al.* 2010). Spalski Landscape Park: Spała [DC40/50], 9 VI 1986, 1 ♂, fig. 3a, 3b, 16 VI 1986, 4 ♂♂, leg. B. Soszyński (Witek *et al.* 2015), 4 VI 2004, 1 ♂, leg. Z. MocarSKI. Modrzewina Nature Reserve near Grójec [DC84], 18 V 2011, 1 ♀, leg. C. Bystrowski. **Małopolska Uplands.** Las Winiarski near Busko-Zdrój [DA79], 18 V 1956, 1 ♂, leg. MIZ PAS team, coll. MIZ PAS (Bańkowska 1961). Włoszczowa [DB23], 4 VI 2009, 1 ♂, fig. 3c, 3e, leg. Ł. Mielczarek. **Lublin-Lvov Uplands (= Wyżyna Lubelsko-Lwowska).** Roztoczański National Park [FB30], 12 VII 1978, 1 ♂, leg. B. Soszyński.

COMPARISON MATERIAL (20 ♂♂, 7 ♀♀). **ESTONIA.** Kose: hill = "Abhang, Kosch" [LF96], 10 VI 1898, 1 ♂, leg. F. Sintenis, coll. MIZ PAS. **LATVIA.** Jeļgawa = “Curonia, Maitau 1906” [FH68], 1 ♀, leg. F. Sintenis, coll. MIZ PAS. **RUSSIA.** Bajkal, Bolsze Koty [WC05], 12 VI 2012, 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀ on flowers of *Spiraea* L., leg. Ł. Mielczarek. Sayan Mountains: Arszan [UC24/25], 22 VI 2012, 1 ♀, leg. Ł. Mielczarek. **UNKNOWN LOCALITY.** [without date], all on a thin pin, half having handwritten label “Scholtz”, 15 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, [leg. H. Scholtz], coll. MNHW, ex. coll. E.J.R. Scholz. [without date], both on a thick tailor pin, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ having handwritten label “Rotermd.”, [leg. W. Rotermund], coll. MNHW, ex. coll. E.J.R. Scholz. [without date and author], 1 ♀, coll. MIZ PAS, ex. coll. P.I.N.G.W. (State Research Institute of Rural Economy in Puławy).

FIG 3. *Mallota megilliformis* (Fallén, 1817). a) male, dorsal view; b) male lateral view; c) living male specimen; d) Łukasz Mielczarek and Robert Żóralski looking for *Mallota* in Spalski Landscape Park, near Cetenka river (photo Z. Mocarski, 2020); e) same living male specimen, dorsal view; f) distribution in Poland: ● verified data, based on material examined, ▲ unverified data

DIAGNOSTIC FEATURES. Bumblebee mimic. Eyes bare; thorax and abdomen covered with long, dense and almost uniform yellow-brown hair; hind tarsi black.

BIOLOGY. In Poland imagines can be observed from the mid of May till the mid of July. Prefers the edges of deciduous forests, especially floodplain forests with very old poplars and elm trees. The larvae develop in deep cavities of such mature and overmature trees. Adult flies visit the upper parts of hawthorns *Crataegus* spp., elderberries *Sambucus* L. and *Spiraea* L. (authors' observations).

DISTRIBUTION. An East European species with a range of occurrence from Fennoscandia, Poland, the Czech Republic and Romania, east into Russia (Pennards *et al.* 2021c, own material). In Poland it is a rare species with an island occurrence characteristic for the border of its range. The historical range of this species in Poland was, however, much wider than nowadays, including such locations like: Kraków [DA24] (Nowicki 1873), Chodecz [CD60] (Sznabl 1881), Gdańsk [CF42] (Bachmann 1858, Czwalina 1893, Żóralski & Kowalczyk 2015), Łągiwnicki Forest in Łódź [CC94] (Kowalczyk & Watała 1991, Kowalczyk *et al.* 1998, Kowalczyk & Majecki 2002, Soszyński *et al.* 2010), "Dolina Mrogi" Nature and Landscape Complex [DC06] (Soszyński *et al.* 2010). Bańkowska (1961) mentioned she had identified one specimen from the material of prof. S. Kapuściński from Wodzisław Śląski [CA14].

CONSERVATION. Species listed in the "Red List of Threatened Animals in Poland" (Palaczyk *et al.* 2002) in category NT (Near Threatened) and in the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species (Pennards *et al.* 2021c) in category LC (Least Concern).

***Mallota tricolor* Loew, 1871**

= *M. japonica* Matsumura, 1916

MATERIAL EXAMINED: (18 ♂♂ 1 ♀). **POLAND. Podlasie-Belarus Uplands.** Białowiecki National Park: Hwoźna river [FD95], section 191, 3 VIII 1969, 1 ♂, leg. B. Soszyński (Soszyński 1999, Pisarska & Soszyński 2001). Biebrza National Park: section 285A "bór ścisły", malaise trap [FE13], 26 V 2007, 1 ♂, leg. A. Kostro-Ambroziak. **Central Polish Lowlands.** Molenda Nature Reserve ad. Tuszyn [CC92], 6 VII 1980, 1 ♂, fig. 4a, 4b, leg. B. Soszyński. Lublinek Forest near Łódź [CC83], 1 VI 1981, 1 ♀, leg. B. Soszyński (Soszyński & Soszyńska-Maj 2011). Spalski Landscape Park: Spała [DC40], 16 VI 1986, 1 ♂, leg. B. Soszyński. Dobieszków near Łódź [DC04], fig. 4e, 7 VI 1988, 1 ♂, 28 VI 1988, 1 ♂, leg. J.K. Kowalczyk, coll. NHUL (Kowalczyk & Watała 1991, Kowalczyk *et al.* 1998, Kowalczyk & Majecki 2002, Soszyński *et al.* 2010). Spalski Landscape Park: Ceteń [DC50], fig. 4c, 4d, 7 VI 2007, 1 ♂, 1 VI 2008, 2 ♂♂, 16-18 VI 2008, 1 ♂, 20 V 2011, 1 ♂, 4 VI 2011, 1 ♂, 5 VI 2011, 1 ♂, 4 VI 2015, 1 ♂, 7 VI 2015, 3 ♂♂, leg. M. Soszyński, det. B. Soszyński (Witek *et al.* 2015). **Silesian-Krakow Uplands (= Wyżyna Śląsko-Krakowska).** Diabelskie Mosty Nature Reserve near Złoty Potok [CB81], oak forest, 17 VI 1957, 1 ♂, leg. J. Kapuściński, coll. MIZ PAS (Trojanowa-Bańkowska 1959).

FIG 4. *Mallota tricolor* Loew, 1871. a) male, dorsal view; b) male lateral view; c) roadside hollow *Ulmus minor* in the village Ceteń (Spalski Landscape Park) where *Mallota tricolor* specimens have been observed for many years; d) same tree, zoom on the trunk with deep hollow; e) Jan Krzysztof Kowalczyk observing *Mallota tricolor* on a senescent Norway maple at a roadside near Dobieszków near Łódź (photo M. Mastalerz, 1988); f) distribution in Poland: ● verified data, based on material examined, ▲ unverified data

COMPARISON MATERIAL (4 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀). **RUSSIA**. Primorsky Krai: Lake Khanka [LK15], 7 VII 2013, 1 ♂, leg. Ł. Mielczarek. Primorsky Krai: Vladivostok [GN37], 27 VII 2013, 1 ♂, leg. Ł. Mielczarek. **UNKNOWN LOCALITY**. [without date and author], 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, coll. MIZ PAS, ex. coll. P.I.N.G.W.

DIAGNOSTIC FEATURES. Bumblebee mimic. Eyes bare; three-colour body hair: anterior half of mesoscutum, scutellum and anterior parts of abdomen lightgray to white, posterior half of mesoscutum and middle parts of abdomen black, tip of abdomen orange; hind tarsi orange.

BIOLOGY. Adults flight period extends from the end of May till the beginning of August, with highest peak in June. This species prefers old trees in parks and along roadside. In the years 2007-2015 male specimens were regularly observed in a microhabitat in Ceteń (Spalski Landscape Park), around the hollow of one field elm *Ulmus minor* Mill., 1773 (fig. 4c, 4d). This particular species of elm is unfortunately critically endangered in Poland and Europe, due to a pandemic disease caused by the fungus *Ophiostoma* Syd. & P. Syd., 1919, causing the dying off of branches, then massive death of trees. The mentioned fungus is one of the most invasive tree pathogens known to the man and in Europe is transmitted by the elm beetle *Scolytus multistriatus* (Marshall, 1802) (Coleoptera, Curculionidae) (Santini & Faccoli 2013).

DISTRIBUTION. East Palearctic species, having in Poland, Lithuania and Finland its western border of the range (Raekunnas & Kerppola 2014). In the past it was found as far as Germany but is currently considered extinct in that country. In Poland, known only from a few sites (fig. 4f) located in the middle and north-east part of the country. Kuntze & Noskiewicz (1938) were first who mention that species from the middle Europe (and as a new species for Poland that time) - it was one specimen sitting on the roadside, then caught by them at the vicinity of Bereżany [= Brzeżany], located in Ukraine. In June 1940, Noskiewicz caught one more specimen on Czartowska Skała near Lviv [= Lwów] (Noskiewicz 1948). We were not able to find material of another locality from the literature: Łagiewnicki Forest near Łódź [CC94] (Kowalczyk & Watała 1991, Kowalczyk *et al.* 1998, Kowalczyk & Majecki 2002, Soszyński *et al.* 2010).

CONSERVATION. Species listed in the “Red List of Threatened Animals in Poland” (Palaczyk *et al.* 2002) in category VU (Vulnerable) and in the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species (Pennards *et al.* 2021d) in category LC (Least Concern).

DISCUSSION

The species of the genus *Mallota* occurring in Poland are primarily found to be associated with deciduous forest, inhabiting microhabitats in single mature and overmature trees, where the immature stages have suitable conditions to develop. These can also be in parks and along roadsides.

Observations of *M. cimbiciformis* and *M. fuciformis* collected in recent years in Poland pertain to man-made substitute habitats, developing in park trees or visiting flowering fruit trees and hawthorn bushes located in ecotone zones (clearings, forest edges) bearing traces of human settlement. That is a signal of adaptation to changing environmental conditions of anthropogenic origin, and seems to slowly become a pattern for many valuable saproxylic insects adapting to new habitats shaped by human activity. Parks and urban forested areas, botanical gardens, cemeteries, alleys and roadsides where favorable microhabitats with mature and overmature decaying trees are preserved enabling scattered populations to thrive (Kotze *et al.* 2022). Indeed, forestry management practices executed over the past decades, such as deforestation (incl. the elimination of naturally valuable, but unnecessary in forestry species as willow, plum tree, hawthorn), afforestation with monoculture, harvesting of mature trees for wood industry and removal of senescent, damaged trees with hollows etc. have caused decline or even loss of valuable invertebrate elements of the fauna (de Groot *et al.* 2016).

M. megilliformis, historically known from multiple sites, was observed during the recent decade only in the most natural areas of north-eastern Poland (Augustów Forest), and we consider its populations are declining. *M. tricolor* is rated as most rare and endangered species of the genus in Poland - except single records reported in old papers, the species nowadays is known only from single record from Biebrza National Park (year 2007) and from one microhabitat in Spalski Landscape Park, with last record dated from 2015.

TABLE 1. Confirmed data on *Mallota* species in Poland. **Breeding sites:** 1 – larvae collected; 2 – observation of females in/around a tree hollow; 3 – observation of males near a tree hollow

SPECIES	FLOWERS VISITED	BREEDING SITES
<i>Mallota cimbiciformis</i>	<i>Euphorbia esula</i> L.	<i>Acer platanoides</i> L. ^{1, 2, 3} <i>Aesculus hippocastanum</i> L. ^{1, 2, 3} <i>Populus nigra</i> L. ³
<i>Mallota fuciformis</i>	<i>Prunus</i> L. <i>Crataegus</i> L.	<i>Acer platanoides</i> L. ¹ <i>Aesculus hippocastanum</i> L. ^{2, 3}
<i>Mallota megilliformis</i>	<i>Sambucus nigra</i> L.	
<i>Mallota tricolor</i>		<i>Ulmus minor</i> Mill. ³

KEY TO *MALLOTA* SPECIES IN POLAND

1. eyes hairy (FIG. 2a) *Mallota fuciformis* (Fabricius, 1794)
- eyes bare (FIG. 1a, 3a, 4a) 2

2. bee-like mimic, abdomen covered with short hairs (FIG. 1e)
..... *Mallota cimbiciformis* (Fallén, 1817)
- bumblebee-like mimic, abdomen covered with long hairs (FIG. 2d,e, 3c,d, 4 a,b) 3

3. hind tarsi black; almost uniform yellow-brown body hair (FIG. 3b)
..... *Mallota megilliformis* (Fallén, 1817)
- hind tarsi orange; three-color body hair: anterior half of mesoscutum, scutellum and
anterior parts of abdomen light-gray to white, posterior half of mesoscutum and
middle parts of abdomen black, tip of abdomen orange (FIG. 4a,b)
..... *Mallota tricolor* Loew, 1871

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PODSUMOWANIE

W niniejszej pracy zrewidowano rodzaj *Mallota* Meigen, 1822 (Diptera, Syrphidae) w oparciu o materiały dostępne w polskich kolekcjach (muzealnych i prywatnych) oraz zebrane w trakcie własnych badań terenowych, a także dokonano podsumowania na temat ich biologii oraz rozmieszczenia w obecnych granicach Polski.

Przeanalizowano łącznie 98 osobników *Mallota*, reprezentujących cztery gatunki: *M. cimbiciformis*, *M. fuciformis*, *M. megilliformis* i *M. tricolor*, a także 33 osobniki spoza Polski lub z nieznaną lokalizacją. Większość opublikowanego materiału pochodzi z ostatnich dwóch dekad.

Występujące w Polsce gatunki z rodzaju *Mallota* związane są z lasami liściastymi, zasiedlając mikrosiedliska (dziuple wypełnione wodą) w dojrzałym drzewostanie. Występują także w parkach miejskich. Wszystkie cztery gatunki są rzadko spotykane, obecne na Czerwonej Liście zwierząt zagrożonych w Polsce (Palaczyk *et al.* 2002) oraz na Czerwonej Liście IUCN (Penards 2001a,b,c,d). Wcześniejsze doniesienia o przedstawicielach tego rodzaju w Polsce (23 publikacje, w tym powtórne cytowania) oparte były na niewielkiej liczbie okazów.

Przedstawiono klucz do oznaczania gatunków występujących w Polsce oraz ich fotografie. Ponadto, w oparciu o obserwacje własne, podsumowano odwiedzane kwiaty oraz miejsca rozwoju (Tab. 1).

<https://pte.up.poznan.pl/pte/dipteron/redakcja.htm>

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